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Case Study

A CASE REPORT OF URETERIC CALCULUS TREATED WITH HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINE, *HYDRANGEA ARBORESCENS* 30

Nayak Chintamani¹, Sahoo Amulya Ratna², Nayak Chaturbhuj³, Prusty Umakanta⁴, Hati Akshaya Kumar⁵, Paital Biswaranjan^{*6}

¹National Institute of Homoeopathy, Kolkata, West Bengal, India.

²Drug Proving Unit of Central Council for Research in Homoeopathy, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India.

³Homoeopathy University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

⁴Regional Research Institute of Homoeopathy, Puri, Odisha, India.

⁵Dr. Abhin Chandra Homoeopathy Medical College and Hospital, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India.

⁶Department of Zoology, College of Basic Science and Humanities, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, India.

Abstract:

Introduction: Urolithiasis denotes formation of stone in the urinary tract; it may be in the kidney, ureter or in the bladder. Urinary stones are considered as a very common cause of morbidity affecting about 5-15% of population. Apart from conservative treatment, shock wave lithotripsy and ureteroscopy are commonly practiced in conventional medicine, in cases of calculi, but these interventions are expensive for the common people and may lead to complications. Here is a case of ureterolithiasis or ureteric calculus successfully treated with homoeopathic organ remedy *Hydrangea arborescens* 30.

Case Profile: A 59 year old female presented with intense pain in loins, especially on the right side and increased frequency of urine. Ultrasonographic report confirmed a solitary stone of 8 mm in the right vesico-ureteric junction. Although advised for surgical intervention, she opted for homoeopathic treatment. She was prescribed with *Hydrangea arborescens* 30 as an organ remedy, on the basis of certain particular symptoms and pathology pertaining to this medicine, after which she was relieved from the intense pain. Numerical Rating Scale (NRS) score showed significant improvement and ultrasonography after 3 months of treatment showed no stone.

Most importantly, although *Hydrangea arborescens* is popularly known as a left-sided medicine for ureteric colic and stone, and the patient had right-sided ureteric stone, yet its local affinity for ureters and pathological affinity for ureteric stones guided its prescription and ultimately, yielded the desired result.

Conclusion: Besides the constitutional or individualized treatment, correct homoeopathic organ specific medicines selected on the basis of important particular symptoms can also be effective. As per the homoeopathic literature, *Hydrangea arborescens* has profound action on the ureters particularly ureteric stones and this case report has justified the fact. However, randomized control trials on action of *Hydrangea arborescens* in cases of urinary stones are suggested.

Key words - Homoeopathy, Ureterolithiasis, Organ remedies, *Hydrangea arborescens*.

Corresponding author:*Paital Biswaranjan,**

Department of Zoology,

College of Basic Science and Humanities,

Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, India

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Urolithiasis is one of the most common afflictions of man. It is estimated that about 5-15% population worldwide develop urolithiasis during their life span [1,2]. High urine calcium levels, obesity, calcium supplements, hyperparathyroidism, gout, certain foods, and drinking fewer fluids are the common risk factors of urinary stones. These are typically classified by their locations: nephrolithiasis (stone in kidney), ureterolithiasis (stone in ureter), and cystolithiasis (stone in urinary bladder) [3]. Stones of less than 5 mm diameter may pass spontaneously without causing any symptoms. However, a stone more than 5 mm diameter can cause blockage of the ureter resulting in severe pain in the lower back or abdomen [2,3]. Stones of size 5–7 mm have a 50% chance of passage and those >7 mm almost always require surgical intervention, as believed in conventional medicine [2]. Currently, ureteroscopy or extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy are common treatment modalities for stones in ureters [4]. Shock wave lithotripsy can cause acute renal injury in 63-85% of patients treated with shock wave lithotripsy demonstrated by C.T. scan and MRI [5,6].

Hydrangea arborescens is one of the most well-known homeopathic medicines for calculus diseases; It is popularly known as “the stone breaker” [7]. *Hydrangea arborescens*, commonly known as seven-barks, it is a remedy in homoeopathy for calculi in urinary tract, with signs and symptoms like deposit of profuse white amorphous salts in urine, urinary calculus, renal colic and bloody urine. It acts on ureter pain in lumbar region, burning pain in urethra and frequent desire for urination; *sharp pain in loins and great thirst* etc [8].

Around 12.7% of India’s population depends solely on Homoeopathy for their health care [2]. Homoeopathy has been proved to be a boon for patients in whom surgery is a risky affair such as aged ones, hypertensive and diabetics or those who are in search of an alternative to surgery [9]. Organopathy implies that a defect in an organ should be corrected, by removing the impairing influence. The appropriate remedy is the agent employed to stimulate repair within that organ [10]. According to Burnett, the significance of emphasis on locality, is that the similitum needs to cover the pathology of the case, not merely matching the superficial

symptom-expression. As said by Burnett, "Experience teaches me that if we are to avoid false issues in treatment we must start with diagnosing, if possible, where the malady is primarily located. At any rate, I find this the shortest way to curing. If this be neglected we not infrequently cover and cure the symptoms, leaving the malady itself more or less untouched"[11]. Keeping this concept of organopathy in the background, *Hydrangea arborescens* was prescribed as an organ remedy and the usefulness of this homoeopathic medicine in the treatment of urinary calculi is highlighted in the present case.

PATIENT INFORMATION

A 59-year-old female of tall, thin, built came to the OPD of National Institute of Homoeopathy, Kolkata on 6th Sept.2017 with intense pain in the right loin for 15-20 days and there was increased frequency of urination. The pain was almost constant without any significant modality. On the numerical rating scale (NRS) (Fig.1), the pain score was 8.

Fig. 1: The pain score of the patient before treatment

The ultrasonographic imaging revealed one 8-millimeter calculus at the right vesico-ureteric junction (Fig. 2, Table 3). She experienced this pain for the first time, which started suddenly and continuing since then. She took some allopathic medication, which provided only temporary relief. Her family history was quite uneventful. In the past, she had suffered from typhoid at the age of 23 years. Hysterectomy done at the age of 45 years due to menorrhagia. She was a married housewife having two well-grown children. She was a non-vegetarian without any specific addiction. She was a chilly patient, had normal appetite and increased thirst; her bowel habits were normal. The patient was introvert with desire for company and music (Table 1).

THEAPAEUTIC INTERVENTION

Table-1: Symptoms considered for prescription

Sl. No.	Symptoms
1.	Stone in ureter
2.	Intense pain in the loin
3.	Frequent desire for urination
4.	Increased thirst

Table-2: Plan of treatment

Date of Visit	Main Symptoms	Numerical Rating Scale(NRS) score for pain	Prescription
6 th Sept.2017	Intense pain in the right loin. Frequent desire for urination.	8	<i>Hydrangea arborescens</i> 30, 5 globules thrice daily for 15 days
26 th Sept.2017	Pain in the right loin decreased. Frequent desire for urination decreased.	5	<i>Hydrangea arborescens</i> 30, 5 globules twice daily for 15 days
17 th Oct.2017	Pain in the right loin decreased significantly. Frequent desire for urination further decreased.	3	<i>Hydrangea arborescens</i> 30, 5 globules twice daily for 15 days
1 st Nov. 2017	Very mild pain in the right loin. No frequent desire for urination.	2	<i>Hydrangea arborescens</i> 30, 5 globules twice daily for 15 days
21 st Nov.2017	No pain in the loin or anywhere in the body. Urination- Normal	0	Placebo, 5 globules twice daily, for 15 days. Patient was asked to do fresh Ultrasound.
20 th Dec. 2017	No pain or any discomfort. USG report shows no stone	0	No medicine

After assessing and analyzing the case, it was found that the patient provided a few significant symptoms only (Table 1) for which, instead of constitutional or individualized treatment, the organopathic approach was followed [12,13]. It was found that '*sharp pain in the loin*' is a determinative or characteristic symptom under the medicine *Hydrangea arborescens* [8]. While looking for other symptoms of the drug, it was also observed that it has not only profound action on the ureters, but also it has two other symptoms, such as '*frequent desire for urination*' and '*great thirst*' which are similar to those of the patient [14].

Hydrangea arborescens was prescribed in 30C potency and was administered in 5 globules per dose

thrice daily for 15 days initially and after improvement, it was reduced to twice daily. This single medicine was prescribed throughout the period of treatment.

FOLLOW UP AND OUTCOME

The patient was advised to report at regular intervals. There was significant decrease in pain and other symptoms of the patient after the first prescription, as reported during subsequent visits (Table 2). There was also decrease in NRS score. Within 3 months, there was complete relief of all the symptoms and ultrasonography showed no stone (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2: Ultrasonography of whole abdomen before the treatment schedule.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Homoeopathic system of medicine has already proved its efficacy in combating various urinary diseases [2, 3, 7, 15-17]. In-vitro studies also suggest favorable action of homoeopathic medicines on renal stones [18]. Our previous studies also indicate about the efficacy of homeopathic remedies on some other critical diseases [19-24]. But it is a common belief in

the conventional system of medicine that stones greater than 7 mm diameter usually require surgical intervention [17]. But there are many instances of dissolution and expulsion of bigger stones through homoeopathic treatment [25, 26]. These cases were mostly treated successfully with polycryst remedies [9] or medicines selected on the basis of constitutional totalities.

Table-3: Ultrasonoreport of whole abdomen before treatment

Liver	Liver is mildly enlarged in size, shape, position and outline. Liver parenchymal echogenicity is mild diffusely increased. No focal lesion is noted in the liver. Intrahepatic biliary radicles are not dilated. Portal and hepatic venous systems are normal
Gall Bladder	Gall Bladder is well distended with normal wall thickness. No intraluminal calculus is noted. No mass is seen
Common bile duct	Common bile duct is not dilated
Spleen	Spleen is normal in size, shape and position. No focal lesion is noted in the splenic parenchyma
Pancreas	Pancreas is normal in size, shape, outline and parenchymal echogenicity. No focal lesion is noted in pancreas. Peripancreatic fat planes are maintained. Pancreatic duct is not dilated
Kidneys	Kidneys are normal in size, shape, position and outline. Renal parenchymal echogenicity is normal with maintained corticomedullary differentiation. No focal lesion, calculus or hydronephrotic changes are noted in kidneys. Right Kidney measures 9.3 cm and Left Kidney measures 9.6 cm in length.
Ureters	Both the ureters are not dilated. A calculus of 8mm. size is noted in the right vesico - ureteric junction.
Urinary Bladder	Urinary bladder is well distended with normal contour and wall thickness. No intraluminal lesion is noted.
Uterus	Uterus is operated
Ovaries	Both ovaries are not visualized
Adnexa	No SOL is noted No free fluid is seen in cul-de-sac
IMPRESSION	Mild hepatomegaly with mild fatty change. Calculus in the right vesico - ureteric junction.

Fig. 3: Ultrasonography of whole abdomen after treatment schedule

Table-4: Ultrasound report of whole abdomen after treatment

Liver	Normal in size, shape, outline and echotexture. No SOL seen. Hepatic veins and intrahepatic biliary radicles not dilated.
Gall Bladder	Gall Bladder is physiologically distended. Wall is of normal thickness. No calculus or SOL is seen within its lumen Ultrasonographic Murphy's sign is negative.
Common bile duct	Not dilated (Measuring 3 mm), No mass or calculus is seen within or around it.
P.V.	Not dilated (Measuring 9 mm)
Pancreas	Pancreas is normal in size, ECHOTEXTURE IS HOMOGENOUSLY BRIGHT; main pancreatic duct is not dilated. No focal SOL or calcification seen within or around the pancreas.
Spleen	Normal in size (Measuring 81 mm). The splenic vein is normal in diameter
Both Kidneys	Normal in size, shape & position. Cortical echotexture is normal, cortico medullary differentiation is maintained. No calculus / hydronephrosis or SOL seen on either side, Right kidney measures 93 mm. Left kidney measures 98 mm
Ureters	Not dilated
Urinary Bladder	Well distended. Wall is of normal thickness. No Intraluminal calculus or SOL
Uterus	NOT VISUALISED (H/O SURGERY)
Ovaries	NOT VISUALISED (? OPERATED)
	No ascites or retroperitoneal lymphadenopathy seen. Iliac fossae do not reveal any collection / mass.
IMPRESSION	- FATTY PANCREAS. - POST-HYSTERECTOMY STATUS.

However, this case was approached differently giving more importance to the sphere of action of the medicine and its pathological symptoms. The most important factor is, although *Hydrangea arborescens* is popularly known as a left-sided medicine, and the patient had right-sided ureteric stone, yet its local affinity for ureters and pathological affinity for ureteric stones, guided its prescription and ultimately yielded the desired result.

So positive response and restoration of health in a gentle manner within short time, without any surgical intervention, in this case, signifies that the dissolution or expulsion of the stones is possible not only by the well-selected constitutional or individualized treatments but also through the organ-specific medicines selected on the basis of their important particular symptoms (Fig. 3) and Table 4). As per the homoeopathy literature, *Hydrangea arborescens* has profound action on the ureters and this case report has justified this. Randomized control trials on action of *Hydrangea arborescens* on ureter or on urinary stones are suggested.

INFORMED CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: None declared

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